

**ТАКТИКА ВЕДЕННЯ ВАГІТНОСТІ ТА ПОЛОГІВ У ПАЦІЄНТОК
ПІЗЬНОГО РЕПРОДУКТИВНОГО ВІКУ З ВАГІТНІСТЮ,
ОТРИМАНОЮ ЗА ДОПОМОГОЮ ДОПОМІЖНИХ
РЕПРОДУКТИВНИХ ТЕХНОЛОГІЙ**

**PREGNANCY AND DELIVERY MANAGEMENT IN PATIENTS OF
ADVANCED MATERNAL AGE WITH A PREGNANCY RESULTING
FROM ASSISTED REPRODUCTION**

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Women of advanced maternal age (AMA) with pregnancies resulting from assisted reproductive technology (ART) are at the group of a high risk of adverse obstetric and perinatal outcomes. The diagnostic-treatment preventative algorithm has been developed in order to minimize risks. Preventive psychological support, early diagnostic and correction of the latent iron deficiency, delivery management with constant CTG-monitoring, elective C-section in case of spontaneous contractions onset absence in terms of 40-41 weeks, massive obstetric hemorrhage (MOH) prevention were the main points of the algorithm.

Objective. To check the effectiveness of the developed algorithm

The prospective study comprised 150 patients divided into three groups of 50 nulliparous women aged 35-45 years with a singleton pregnancy in the cephalic presentation: the main group (MG) included patients after ART who had pregnancy and delivery management according to the algorithm; patients with a pregnancy after ART from the comparison group (C-nG) and patients with a spontaneous pregnancy from the control group (C-IG) had the standard care.

Results. The frequency of normal and CS delivery did not differ significantly in the study groups. However, the frequency of urgent CS in the MG was lower than in the C-nG and in the C-IG ($p < 0.05$). The average blood loss volumes during vaginal delivery and CS in the MG were lower than in the C-nG (263.04 \pm 10.8 ml vs. 328.5 \pm 19.17 ml, and 686.67 \pm 17.05 ml vs. 813.67 \pm 47.26 ml, respectively, $p < 0.05$) and did not differ significantly from the C-IG. Gestational anemia at terms

of 35-37 weeks and postpartum anemia were less often diagnosed in the MG than in the C-nG and C-IG (2% vs. 30% & 18%, and 2% vs. 56% & 44%, respectively, $p < 0.05$). The average length of hospital stay after delivery in the MG was also shorter than in the C-nG ($p < 0.05$).

The number of patients at high risk of developing depression in the postpartum was significantly lower in the MG in contrast to the C-nG. At terms of 22-24 weeks the numbers of patients with high trait (TA) and state anxiety (SA) levels in the MG and C-nG were significantly higher than in the control group ($p < 0.05$). However, at terms of 35-37 weeks significant increase was observed in TA and SA levels in C-nG and C-IG in contrast to the MG. The number of patients with high TA and SA levels in the MG stayed significantly lower than in the C-nG. A gradual decrease in TA and SA levels in all groups was observed in the postpartum period, but the differences between the groups remained consistent. All patients suffered from insomnia with the pregnancy progression, but average PSQI values at terms of 35-37 weeks of gestation and 6-8 weeks after delivery were significantly lower in the MG compared to the C-nG (7.5 +/- 0.3 vs. 8.7 +/- 0.3 and 7.4 +/- 0.3 vs 8.3 +/- 0.3, $p < 0.05$).

Conclusions. The use of the preventive algorithm in AMA women after ART significantly decreased the number of urgent CS, blood loss volume, MOH frequency; validly reduced the risks of severe anemia; anxiety levels, improved sleep quality and consequently improved the quality of life of women and prevented adverse obstetric, perinatal and mental outcomes.